

GIScience 2016 Workshop

Rethinking the ABCs: *Agent-Based Models* and Complexity Science in the age of Big Data, CyberGIS, and Sensor Networks

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Edited by

Daniel G. Brown

Eun-Kyeong Kim

Liliana Perez

Raja Sengupta

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About the Workshop

A broad scope of concepts and methodologies from complexity science – including Agent-Based Models, Cellular Automata, network theory, chaos theory, and scaling relations – has contributed to a better understanding of spatial/temporal dynamics of complex geographic patterns and process.

Recent advances in computational technologies such as Big Data, Cloud Computing and CyberGIS platforms, and Sensor Networks (i.e. the Internet of Things) provides both new opportunities and raises new challenges for ABM and complexity theory research within GIScience. Challenges include parameterization of complex models with volumes of georeferenced data being generated, scale model applications to realistic simulations over broader geographic extents, explore the challenges in their deployment across large networks to take advantage of increased computational power, and validate their output using real-time data, as well as measure the impact of the simulation on knowledge, information and decision-making both locally and globally via the world wide web.

The scope of this workshop is to explore novel complexity science approaches to dynamic geographic phenomena and their applications, addressing challenges and enriching research methodologies in geography in a Big Data Era. The topics include:

1. Multisensor Data Fusion for parameterizing complex models
 - a. Handling the 5Vs (Volume, Velocity, Variety, Value, and Veracity)
 - b. Multi-scale interactions in geographic complex phenomena
 - c. Semantic interoperability
2. Integrating theory with practice:
 - a. Big data analytics integrated with complexity theories
 - b. Spatiotemporal analysis in complexity theories
 - c. Dynamic geo-social network analysis
 - d. Observer-Expectancy effect of real-time simulations
 - e. Scaling relations (power laws) in geography
 - f. Game theoretic approach to geographic problems

3. Output Validation:

- a. Can modeled pattern or process outputs be validated with real-time data?
- b. How can complex models output be visualized and communicated?
- c. How can increased use of massive sensitivity analyses improve process validation?
- d. Observer-Expectancy effect of real-time models' simulations

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Extended Abstracts

An Adaptive Agent-Based Model of Homing Pigeons: A Genetic Algorithm Approach

Francis Oloo¹ and Gudrun Wallentin¹

¹ University of Salzburg, Interfaculty Department of Geoinformatics (ZGIS), Schillerstrasse 30-5020 Salzburg, Austria

{francisomondi.oloo,gudrun.wallentin}@sbg.ac.at

Abstract. Conventional ABMs are formalized from well established theory of the systems of interest. Simulation outcomes are then used to valid of the conceptual understanding. Integration of real-time sensor data streams into modelling workflows opens up the possibility to simulate on the go where calibration and validation procedures are automated processes and are executed during simulation runs. Real-time simulation models result in surprising patterns and increasingly well calibrated parameters and rule sets. Which raises question on the epistemological implications of data-driven modelling to traditional system analysis and modelling approaches? In this contribution, we explore this question by implementing a flocking model that evolves in real-time. Specifically, genetic algorithm is used to simulate optimum parameters to describe trajectories of homing pigeons based on emulated GPS-sensor stream that updates the model continuously. Validity of the approach is compared to the conventional approach and results are discussed in the light of calibration uncertainty, repeatability, and transferability.

1 Introduction

Traditionally, models have been built from well-established theory of the underlying systems and empirical data is introduced at later stages for calibration and validation in an iterative process of exploration, resulting in a set of parameters that produce the optimal representation of the underlying system. Recent developments in data capture and transmission, specifically in sensor technology invite the incorporation of the rich data emanating from such platforms into modelling and simulation environments. The emergence of miniaturized sensors and intelligent sensor networks to monitor real-world phenomena provides an opportunity of using sensor data streams to investigate, understand and represent local level behaviour of system entities and the influence of such behaviour on overall system outcomes. That sensors can dynamically capture and transmit spatio-temporal characteristics in real-time also raises the question on the suitability of traditional methods of model specification, calibration, and validation.

In this contribution, we implement an agent-based model (ABM) of adaptive rule sets of homing pigeons during their flight from a release site to a home loft. It is our view that concepts of adaptation and emergence which are inherent in ABMs [1] can provide the entry point for incorporation of sensor observations into ABMs by facilitating automation of model calibration and implementation of adaptive rule sets of agent behaviours. Furthermore, sensor streams can potentially influence model specifications by providing continuous feedback on aspects of the systems of interest and thus provide information on the adaptation among the agents represented in the model [2]. Adaptive rule sets are important in understanding emergence in complex systems and have been applied to study movement patterns of fish [3] and to model the influence of feeding, growth and survival probabilities in habitat selection among salmonids [4].

Adaptation within ABMs is hinged on the ability of agents to sense their environments, learn about possible actions to take in different circumstances and respond to stimuli from other agents or from the environment [5]. Learning within ABM has been achieved through reinforcement learning [6], evolutionary (genetic) algorithms and through machine learning methods [7]. However, the implementations of these methods have been through theory driven approaches to modelling. Spatial learning is the precursor to successful adaptation and has been identified as one of the challenges to representation of spatially aware agents [6]. We thus hypothesize that real-time high resolution spatio-temporal data streams can facilitate the implementation of spatial learning and help in understanding and representation of local spatial-temporal behaviour of agents. In this task, we use genetic algorithms to model the navigation of homing pigeons from a release site to a known loft.

2 Methods

GPS trajectories in this study were sourced from an experimental research on leadership among homing pigeons in Seuzach Switzerland [8]. The data, contained information on five separate homing flights with each flight capturing the coordinates; speed and flight height of at least 7 pigeons at a time interval of 0.25 seconds.

A flocking and navigation model of the pigeons from the release site to the home loft was implemented in Netlogo. The purpose of this model was to identify the optimal parameters for simulation of navigation of homing pigeons which are represented as autonomous agents. Agents can sense other agents in their vicinity and the environment and make independent decisions with the goal of flying home in a flock and by following realistic flight paths. Two sets of pigeon agents are represented in the model; “real” birds that use the empirical data from the emulated GPS trajectories to navigate and simulated birds that learn from the real birds and use flocking and navigation rules to arrive at the homing loft. At each time step, step distance, relative turn-angle, sinuosity of flight path and the mean distance between flock mates is evaluated. Additionally, during the learning runs of the model, a measure of fitness is calculated for the simulated birds.

Simulated flights of the birds are controlled by flocking and navigation rules. Flocking rules are modified from Reynolds flocking model [9] and are guided by alignment,

coherence and separation procedures which are achieved through maximum alignment turns, maximum coherence turns, maximum separation turns and minimum separation distance. Navigation behaviour is guided by an elevation turn angles which allows agents to fly along a topographic isoline and loft-turn which is an angle that specifies the general direction towards the home loft. Additionally, visible distance and the maximum view angle of the agents are specified by corresponding parameters.

Initial calibration resulted in a set of suitable parameters for simulation of flocking and navigation behaviour of the simulated agents without learning from the emulated GPS tracks. These set of parameters which included maximum alignment turn, maximum coherence turn, maximum separation turn, maximum loft turn, maximum elevation turn, vision distance, maximum view angle, minimum and maximum step distance provided the elements for encoding a chromosome of candidate navigation parameters. A disturbance was introduced to the elements of individual agent chromosomes adding a random value from a normal distribution with a mean of 0.0 and standard deviation of 0.1. Genetic algorithm creates a generic range of optimal parameters to simulate the flight behaviour of homing pigeons from the release sites to the homing loft. Student's t-test at 95% confidence interval was used to compare the simulated and observed flight trajectories.

3 Results

The resulting model was executed 50 times, in each run, chromosomes of the final generation of agents and the fitness values were recorded. Model runs resulting in negative fitness values at the end of the simulation were excluded in subsequent analysis. Density charts of optimal range and distribution of the nine model parameters are shown in Fig. 1.

A random normal distribution with a mean and standard deviation of each of the respective simulated parameters was used to encode the corresponding elements of a chromosome for subsequent verification and validation. Flight 5 from the data was used for validation. Fig. 2 shows the density distribution of relative turn angles and the average step distances from observed and simulated flight paths. In both cases the state variables are normally distributed. Furthermore, results of Student's T-test showed that the mean value of relative turn angles from the validation data was 0.02 while the corresponding value for the simulated data was -0.08 (p-value >0.05). However, in the case of step distance, the average value from the validation data and the corresponding value from the simulated data were equal, each at 4.5m (p-value <0.05).

Fig. 1. Density distribution of the simulated model parameters

Fig. 2. Density chart of relative turn angle and average step distance of observed and simulated (dotted lines) pigeon flight paths

4 Conclusion

Whereas agents presented herewith were not trained to remember all the possible states of their environment, parameters resulting from the genetic algorithm were able to successfully simulate the core state variables including relative turn-angle and step-distance which are vital in describing animal movement trajectories. Imitated data streams successfully represented dynamic spatial and temporal characteristics of autonomous pigeon agents thus providing a basis on which to compare the simulated state variables against corresponding empirical values during the life of a model, thus giving credence to the hypothesis that dynamic data streams from sensor observations can be incorporated into agent based models to improve the understanding of moving organisms. More importantly, availability of dynamic and high resolution data streams makes it possible to develop models without over-reliance on the theories and assumptions hence a data-driven approach to modelling. Additionally, by providing instantaneous calibration and verification of models during the model run results in robust parameters and hence improving their transferability to other settings and scenarios. Finally, genetic algorithm ensures an evolution of optimal solutions and parameters and thus making a strong case its consideration in data-driven hypothesis generation and knowledge discovery.

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Developing High Fidelity, Data Driven, Verified Agent Based Models of Coupled Socio-Ecological Systems of Alaska Fisheries

Martin Cenek¹, Maxwell Franklin¹

¹ University of Alaska Anchorage, Anchorage AK 99508, USA

mcenek@uaa.alaska.edu, mefranklin@alaska.edu

1 Extended Abstract

Alaska salmon fisheries are a source of commercial revenue, renewable subsistence resource, cultural identity, and recreational destination for Alaskans, native populations, and out of state eco-tourists alike. We constructed a high fidelity, adaptable, data-driven agent based model that generalizes the socio-ecological dynamics of Kenai River, Alaska. Interactions among the model’s agents can be altered to study the impact of fishing regulation changes or salmon run-timing dynamics. Agents are driven by stochastic principles derived from 35 years of integrated data including salmon runs, municipality management reports, and Alaska Department of Fish and Game management reports. Longitudinal and seasonal correlations between the model’s simulation outputs and the reported system measurements are used to validate the model.

To model accurate salmon agents counts, we reconstructed the temporal distribution of the salmon run by taking 35 years of reported sonar counts as the baseline and adding the harvest of the major stakeholder groups. The genetic sampling of randomly selected salmon caught by the drift gillnet, set gillnet, as well as test fisheries at the mouth of Upper Cook Inlet is used to determine how much salmon caught by the off-shore fishermen were returning to the Kenai River watershed instead of the rest of the inlet tributaries [2]. Time frames of these harvests are reported alongside estimated harvest from genetic sampling by gear type.

Salmon runs were grouped into four categories by their overall characteristics of run-timing dynamics. We used the sonar records to categorize the run-timing patterns using feature-scaling to filter daily sockeye counts with values $x' \geq 0.5$ (Equation 1). The temporally aligned and weekly binned series of filtered sonar data for 35 years were mutually compared. The distributions with high similarity were grouped into the four resulting prototype categories. Averaging the series in each prototype category produced the generalized baseline time-series distribution of the salmon runs with variance margins (Fig. 1).

$$x' = (x - \min(x)) / (\max(x) - \min(x)) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3. The feature scaling with $x' \geq 0.5$ classification of each sockeye salmon run-timing dynamics for 35 years of reported sonar data into one of four characteristic classes. Each plot shows the averaged run distribution and the standard error. The run types III, IV, and III-IV are named after the peak location in the returning salmon run in week 3, 4, 3 – 4 of the season respectively. The type III-IV-V has multiple peaks in weeks 3, 4, and 5 of the season.

Salmon harvest represents the coupling between the fishermen effort to catch fish and the salmon run, in addition to other factors such as gear choice, fishing location, and fishing efficiency. The harvest reports are the aggregate socioecological metrics used to express the interaction dynamics between the social and ecological systems. Catch Per Unit of Effort (CPUE) is one such measure. CPUE can be used as an index of both stock abundance [4, 5] and stakeholder effort [1]. We decoupled the temporal CPUE distributions into the constituent system dynamics and using the previously reconstructed salmon run-timing distributions, we were able to infer the social behavior that was not previously measured or reported. Building the interaction dynamics of the model’s fishermen agents is a reverse inference process. The agents have to have the same behavior as the social behavior inferred from CPUE and when the model’s fishermen agents interact with salmon agents, the correlation between the model’s CPUE output and the measured CPUE must be high.

The model is validated by calculating the mutual correlations between the reported data by the management agencies (ADFG, Kenai Borough) and the measured distributions from the model's output. The sonar instrumented salmon counts are used to verify the cumulative impact of commercial set and drift gillnet fleet combined with the dipnet harvest. Fig. 2 (a) and (b) show the validation of the individual stakeholder group behaviors and salmon behaviors in the context of dipnet effort and harvest by correlating measured data and the model's output within each system of the coupled systems dynamics. For each year, the model was seeded with the appropriate number of stakeholders and returning run dynamics to assess the model's accuracy at capturing observed social system dynamics and ecological dynamics. Fig. 2 (a) and (b) show both intra-system dynamics metrics with correlation values $R^2 \geq 0.83$.

Fig. 4. Validating Social System Dynamics of (a) dipnet effort and (b) dipnet harvest. Seasonal effort and harvest data from the model output and historical records were cross-correlated to validate the social dynamics of the model. Ecological System Dynamics are also reflected in dipnet harvest (b). Sub-figures (c) and (d) show validation of the coupled system dynamics using (c) dipnet CPUE from data and (d) the model's output. The seasonal data of CPUE used permit days fished versus harvest.

Measuring model outcomes with simple metrics loses the information about how the goal was met, or how the nature of interactions between the model's agents changed to produce the system-wide (outcomes) dynamics. Visually inspecting each model behavior is infeasible for the combinatorial parameter space. We developed a statistical based toolbox called Geometry of Behavioral Spaces that records agents' behaviors independent of the knowledge of the parameter space that drives the model and produces a state-space transition network that characterizes the agent behaviors [3].

We described a construction of a high fidelity ABM from data sources with high diversity, unknown accuracy, and various reporting frequencies. We constructed collections of temporal distributions that described the individual social and ecological system dynamics as well as the coupled system dynamics. The regressions between the data collections representing instrumented measurements and the model's outputs measure the accuracy of the model's construction in generalizing the socio-ecological systems. The data collections from instrumented measurements often contained multiple distributions describing the same observed phenomena. By cross-correlating these equivalency distributions, we performed manual ensemble learning to establish trustworthiness of each source distribution.

Future research includes implementing plausible future scenarios identified in a series of participatory stakeholder engagement meetings to understand how the coupled system dynamics will change in each scenario. The social scenarios include using dipnetters as a means for managing escapement, alteration of commercial gillnet fishing gear for reducing non-target species by-catch, and using sports fishermen as a means for controlling escapement. The ecological scenarios include compressing the salmon run duration by two weeks while maintaining the abundance and inversely keeping the overall dynamics while reducing the overall salmon abundance. Finally, we will use the statistical toolbox (Geometry of Behavioral Spaces Framework) to analyze agent behavior to understand system outcomes and model changes in terms of agent behaviors.

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Extracting and Visualizing Geo-Social Semantics from the User Mention Network on Twitter

Caglar Koylu¹

¹ Department of Geographical and Sustainability Sciences, University of Iowa, 316 Jessup Hall,
Iowa City, IA 52242, USA

caglar-koylu@uiowa.edu

Abstract. This paper introduces an approach for extracting and visualizing geo-social semantics of user mentions on Twitter. The approach consists of three steps. First, data filtering and processing is performed to construct a directed area-to-area mention network in which tweets are aggregated into flow bins between geographic areas. Second, using flow bins as documents, a probabilistic topic model is employed to detect a collection of topics, and classify each area-to-area flow into a mixture of topics with differing probabilities. Third, for each topic, a modularity graph of mentions is obtained and visualized using a flow map and a topic cloud to infer semantics from the set of frequently co-occurring words for each topic. To demonstrate, a dataset of 19 million geo-tagged mentions during the primary elections (Feb-Jun, 2016) in the U.S. were analyzed. The results highlight changing patterns of symmetry, distance and clustering of flows by the topic of content.

1 Introduction

Previous studies have utilized user generated textual content such as geo-tagged tweets and messages exchanged in location-based social networks (LBSN) to study the effect of geographic proximity on social interactions [1-3]; the influence of information diffusion and social networks on real-world geographic events, such as demonstrations, protests, and group activities [4]; and the structural and geographic characteristics of the communication network [5-7]. Such studies use information flows to model social interactions, but often ignore the content of the information exchanged between the individuals of the network.

A variety of computational and semantic analysis techniques have been developed to infer human behavior, ideological and attitudinal similarity between individuals [8], common topics and way of speaking [9], group identities [10], demographic and socio-economic characteristics [11] from large volumes of user-generated textual data. Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) [12, 13] has been successfully employed to detect geographic events, and recommend places and friends based on user location and similarity of shared content between users in LBSNs. Despite these efforts, there has been little work that

focuses on understanding of geographic patterns of interpersonal communication and how the common topics of information vary based on the geographic distance and characteristics of locations [14].

We introduce an approach for extracting and visualizing geo-social semantics from the big data of user mentions on Twitter. The approach consists of three steps. First, data filtering and processing is performed and a bi-directional area-to-area mention network is constructed. In an area-to-area mention network, the original locations of tweets are aggregated into a small set of areas (e.g., counties) and mentions are combined into flow bins between these geographical areas. Second, flow bins are used to train a probabilistic topic model which generates a collection of topics and classify each flow bin into a mixture of topics with differing probabilities. Third, for each topic, a modularity graph of mentions is obtained and visualized using a flow map and a topic cloud to infer semantics from the set of frequently co-occurring words for each topic. To demonstrate, geo-tagged tweets within the Contiguous U.S. during presidential primaries and caucuses between February 1, 2016 and June 14, 2016 were collected through Twitter’s streaming API.

2 Data processing and filtering

The data consisted of 284,868,345 tweets, and 4,571,070 million distinct users. We removed tweets from non-personal accounts (e.g., weather, emergency, and job ads), and external sources such as pictures and check-ins (e.g., Instagram, Foursquare); users with more than 3000 followers; and users whose velocities (i.e., equals to the distance divided by time between two consecutive tweets) are above (1,000km/h) which would indicate spam users and bots. After the initial filtering, the number of tweets decreased to 75.0% (213,649,745) and the users to 88% (4,050,523).

A Twitter user can reply or mention other users by including their @username in her tweet. When a user A (sender) mentions user B (recipient), the tweet include only the location of the sender. The location of the recipient in a mention can be derived only if the recipient has a geo-tagged tweet in the sample. Among the filtered tweets, 45% (95,855,784) include a user mention, and 65.0% (2,632,840) of the users mentioned another user in a tweet at least once. The recipient’s location was successfully extracted in 19.80% (19,046,949) of all mention tweets to form a network of geo-tagged user mentions.

3 Topic Modeling

Given a collection of textual documents (e.g., books, articles, emails), LDA models a collection of k topics as a multinomial distribution over words within these documents.

$$P(Z|W, D) = \frac{W_{Z+\beta w}}{\text{total tokens in } Z + \beta} * D_{Z+\alpha}$$

The probability that word W came from topic Z , is calculated as the normalized product of the frequency of W in Z ($W_{Z+\beta_w}$) and the number of other words in document D that already belong to Z ($D_{Z+\alpha}$). β and β_w are hyper-parameters that represent the chance that word W belongs to topic Z even if it is nowhere else associated with Z .

Training a topic model with short documents (i.e., individual tweets) results in unstable classifications with increased uncertainty due to the severe data sparsity [15]. To alleviate the problem, previous work combined tweets into temporal [16], spatio-temporal [17], and user bins [18]. We combine tweets into area-to-area (i.e., county-to-county) flow bins to capture interpersonal conversations between geographic areas. Each user is assigned to a home county, and mention tweets are added into a flow bin based on the home counties of the recipient and sender of each mention. Each tweet is added to an origin-destination flow bin only once to avoid duplicate content when a tweet includes multiple mentions between the same county pair.

The density of geo-tagged mentions by distance (Fig. 1) support the findings of previous research that the probability of a user mention is high between users with closer geographic proximity [19]. 46% of the geo-tagged mentions had both the recipient and sender within the same county, 70% were within the same state, and only 30% were between states.

Fig. 5. Density of geo-tagged user mentions by distance (in km)

Great variation in volume between flow bins within states and between states distort the results of LDA and undermine the topical heterogeneity of the model. Thus, we separated the flow bins into two groups: within state, and between state; and constructed a separate LDA model for each. In this paper, we report the results of our analysis on user mentions in which the recipient and sender are from different states, in order to capture the geographical variation of the topical content among long-distance interpersonal communication.

In order to alleviate the bias from small bins, we further filtered out the flow bins that have less than 100 tweets and 10 users before training the topic model. While the number

of flow bins (or county pairs) decreased from 350,295 to 49,436; the volume of mentions was reduced by only 13%. We used the Mallet toolkit [20] to implement the LDA model and trained a set of topic models with differing number of topics (20, 50, and 100), number of iterations (2000), and evaluated the topical overlap using cosine similarity. We selected 50 topics as it produced the less overlapping topics than 100, and more distinct topics than 20.

4 Mapping Modularity Flows

The topic model classifies each flow bin with a mixture of topics with differing probabilities. For example, a flow from county A to county B may be comprised of 50% topic 5, 30% topic 2, 10% topic 32, and 10% in other topics. Among a set of fuzzy classification of flow bins, one may isolate each topic to create a separate graph and estimate the weight of a link by multiplying the probability of isolated topic by the volume of user mentions on that link.

Although the number of mentions have been significantly reduced after excluding within-state mentions, county-to-county pairs still form a complex graph with a large number of links that requires further simplification. One can reduce the graph by graph partitioning and regionalization [21, 22] which combines unit areas into a smaller set of natural regions where there are more flows within regions than across regions. In order to ease the interpretation of our results, and reveal user mention patterns at the state level, we aggregate county pairs into state-to-state user mention flows for each topic and calculate a modularity measure to select the flows that are above expectation [22]. Expected number of mentions on a link is calculated as:

$$EM(O, D) = F_O F_D f(O, D) / (F_S^2 - \sum_{i=0}^n F_i^2)$$

where F_O is the number of mentions originated from state O, F_D is the number of times that state D is mentioned, $f(O, D)$ is the number of mentions from state O to state D, F_S is the number of mentions between all states, and $\sum_{i=0}^n F_i^2$ is used to remove within-state expectations. Finally, modularity of a link O-D for topic Z is calculated as:

$$MOD_Z(O, D) = P_Z (AM - EM)$$

where P_Z is the probability of topic Z, AM is actual number of mentions, and EM is expected number of mentions on the link O-D.

5 Results

Fig. 2 illustrates modularity flows of two topic graphs: (a) NBA finals (b) democratic primaries. The mentions on NBA finals have symmetrical flows which suggest on-going conversations between pairs of states. A distinct asymmetrical flow is observed from Ohio

to Florida, which suggests Cleveland fans mentioning Heat fans, but their tweets are not replied. On the other hand, the mentions on democratic primaries are dominated by asymmetrical flows of mentions. The three big states CA, NY and TX receive more mentions than expected. One distinct difference between the two topics is that mentions on democratic primaries reach out to longer distance states without reciprocating conversations, whereas NBA is being discussed between close by states with on-going conversations.

Fig. 6. State-to-state modularity flows of user mentions for two distinct topics: (a) NBA Finals (Prob: 0.12) (b) primaries and caucuses (Prob: 0.15). The width and color value of each flow is proportional to its modularity value. Node size illustrates the total modularity; and blue circles depict negative net flow whereas red circles depict positive net flows. Word clouds illustrate the set of frequently co-occurring words for each topic where the size of each word is proportional to its probability of co-occurrence or popularity within that topic.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

We introduced a novel approach for extracting and visualizing geo-social semantics from the bi-directional user mention network on Twitter. The results highlighted distinct geographic patterns of symmetry, distance and clustering for user mentions. A major limitation of this study is that the temporal variation in topics is ignored. Future work is needed to incorporate temporal flow binning, and train the topic model to extract temporally varying patterns of mention topics between origin-destination pairs.

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Geospatial Agent-Based Approach for Modelling Biological Control Dynamics of Forest Insect Infestation

Taylor M. Anderson^{1*}, Suzana Dragičević¹

¹ Department of Geography, Simon Fraser University, 8888 University Drive, Burnaby, Canada

{taylora, suzanad}@sfu.ca

Abstract. Geospatial agent-based models (ABM) can be designed to explore scenarios related to propagation of various spatio-temporal phenomena including forest insect infestation and related management strategies. The main objective of this study is to develop an ABM to represent dynamics between the two forest insects, the emerald ash borer (EAB) *Agrilus planipennis* and the *Tetrastichus planipennisi* (TP), a stingless wasp used as a biological control larval parasitoid for EAB. The model is implemented on real geospatial datasets from the City of Oakville, Canada, a region much affected with EAB infestation. For that purpose, an EAB-TP ABM is developed in order to simulate spatio-temporal dynamics and the biological control of EAB infestation using TP. Results indicate that ABM makes a suitable approach for the representation of EAB-TP dynamics for the simulation of EAB biological control, useful in forest and pest management.

1 Introduction

The eradication of the emerald ash borer (EAB) an invasive wood-boring beetle native to Asia is of primary focus for forest management in southwestern Ontario, Canada, to prevent further decline of North American ash trees. Since visible symptoms of infested trees are limited, preventing direct management via insecticides, and native predators are lacking, eradication measures have been extended to biological control, a strategy that uses natural enemies to control pest populations. Pest-parasitoid interactions between the *Tetrastichus planipennisi* (TP) and EAB result in the parasitism and death of EAB larvae by TP larvae, resulting in a 1-2% reduction of EAB within one year and up to 30% after four years (Duan et al. 2013).

In the biological control of any forest insect infestation, it is important to understand the spatial patterns of insects' dispersal, interactions, and dynamics, but this information can be difficult to obtain from the field. Alternatively, an agent-based model (ABM) can be used as a virtual laboratory to simulate these patterns and better understand complexity of the

* Corresponding author

infestation dynamics and its control with natural predators. Existing EAB models use differential equations (Barlow et al. 2014) and diffusion models (Muirhead et al. 2006), however are limited in their representation of spatio-temporal complexity inherent to insect infestation processes (With 2002). Specifically, EAB infestation can be conceptualized as a complex system, whereby heterogeneous individuals interact at local level and across a varying spatial environment and generate large scale patterns of infestation (BenDor et al, 2006; Anderson and Dragicevic, 2016a).

In order to extend existing modelling efforts and address the complexity of EAB infestation, Anderson and Dragicevic (2015) developed an ABM of EAB infestation that is capable of capturing the complexity inherent to insect infestation processes by representing heterogeneous individuals or agents that interact within a geospatial environment from which patterns of infestation emerge. ABMs can be used for scenario development, for example, optimizing release strategies of TP for the control of EAB. However no such modelling approaches can be found in the literature that represents the pest-parasitoid interactions and spatio-temporal dynamics of both EAB and TP insects. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to develop the geospatial ABM to simulate spatio-temporal dynamics and the biological control of EAB infestation using TP.

2 Methods

2.1 Data Sets, Study Site, and Model Overview

The developed ABM modeling approach is implemented on geospatial datasets representing the Town of Oakville, Ontario, Canada, a leader in EAB infestation data collection, management, and eradication. The epicenter of EAB infestation in Oakville, first discovered in 2008, lies in the North Iroquois Ridge community. The Town of Oakville developed GIS datasets containing ash tree inventory with location and attributes for tree species and the delimitation of EAB infestations for the Town of Oakville observed in 2009, providing the actual EAB spread rate of 1.977 km/year.

The EAB-TP ABM has been developed representing two years of insect dispersal in the Town of Oakville (2008-2009) and to measure the effects of the TP interactions on the population of EAB. This model implements the release of 600 TP agents, the minimum number of TP required for release reported in the literature (Gould et al. 2016), at the epicenter of EAB infestation, in June 2009, one year after EAB infestation begins in the region. In order to compare and optimize the biological control, an EAB-Baseline ABM has been developed to represent EAB infestation only. The model expands from the existing ABM of EAB infestation (Anderson and Dragicevic 2015), and was tested against real datasets delimiting EAB extent and validated with 72% accuracy in simulating the location of EAB infestation. Fifty simulation runs have been executed for both developed models and the simulation results are combined in order to determine where the spatial extent of EAB and TP spread occurs on average. The averaged simulation results from each model are compared in order to determine the simulated impact of TP on EAB populations.

2.2 Agents, State Variables, and Model Processes

The ABM includes agents that represent EAB insects, EAB larvae, TP insects, TP larvae, and ash trees. Agents are programmed to behave as their real world counterparts by incorporating biological information documented in the literature into the agents design in the form of state variables and parameters. State variables describe the state of the agent at a given point in time i.e. age, location. Parameters describe the capabilities of a particular agent over its life time i.e. maximum flight distance/day, chance of fertility, maximum number of offspring.

Dispersal of both EAB and TP agents is governed by their preferences for specific host tree characteristics (size, type, health) and spatial distributions. Population dynamics emerge from the local interactions between EAB and TP larvae agents. For example, for every one EAB larvae, 5-122 TP larvae will feed on it, killing it, and collectively reducing the EAB population (Duan et al. 2013). This interaction is simulated in the model where the number of TP larvae agents it will take to kill an EAB agent is generated randomly from 5-122 and once this threshold has been reached, the EAB agent is removed from the simulation.

3 Results

The simulation results and parasitism of EAB larvae by TP larvae over time are presented in Fig. 1. The comparison of number of larvae between the simulation results obtained from EAB-TP and EAB-Baseline agent-based models indicates a parasitism rate of 1.8% following the first year of TP release. The simulation result is consistent with the parasitism rate recorded in the literature of 1-2% (Duan et al. 2013).

4 Conclusions

Representation of insect infestation as a complex system using ABM can help to understand and analyze implications of biological control, specifically in understanding how interactions at a small scale generate emergent parasitoid-pest dynamics. The results indicate that an ABM is a suitable approach for capturing the EAB-TP interaction dynamics. Currently, biological control strategies using TP for EAB management are non-specific. The further development of several scenarios to simulate how the EAB population will respond to variations TP release densities, number of TP release points, and timing of release using the proposed EAB-TP ABM would be beneficial for planning by forest pest managers when time and resources for data collection are limited (Anderson and Dragicevic, 2016b).

Fig. 7. The spatial patterns of EAB and TP spread for (A) June 2009, (B) September 2009 and (C) parasitism of EAB by TP over time.

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Short Abstracts

A Complex-Network Perspective on Alexander's Wholeness*

Bin Jiang¹

¹ Engineering and Sustainable Development, Division of GIScience, University of Gävle, SE-801 76 Gävle, Sweden

bin.jiang@hig.se

"Nature, of course, has its own geometry. But this is not Euclid's or Descartes' geometry. Rather, this geometry follows the rules, constraints, and contingent conditions that are, inevitably, encountered in the real world."

Christopher Alexander et al. (2012)

Abstract. The wholeness, conceived and developed by Christopher Alexander, is what exists to some degree or other in space and matter, and can be described by precise mathematical language. However, it remains somehow mysterious and elusive, and therefore hard to grasp. This paper develops a complex network perspective on the wholeness to better understand the nature of order or beauty for sustainable design. I bring together a set of complexity-science subjects such as complex networks, fractal geometry, and in particular underlying scaling hierarchy derived by head/tail breaks – a classification scheme and a visualization tool for data with a heavy-tailed distribution, in order to make Alexander's profound thoughts more accessible to design practitioners and complexity-science researchers. Through several case studies (some of which Alexander studied), I demonstrate that the complex-network perspective helps reduce the mystery of wholeness and brings new insights to Alexander's thoughts on the concept of wholeness or objective beauty that exists in fine and deep structure. The complex-network perspective enables us to see things in their wholeness, and to better understand how the kind of structural beauty emerges from local actions guided by the 15 fundamental properties, and in particular by differentiation and adaptation processes. The wholeness goes beyond current complex network theory towards design or creation of living structures.

Keywords: theory of centers, living geometry, Christopher Alexander, head/tail breaks, and beauty

* This abstract is that of the newly published paper: Jiang B. (2016), A complex-network perspective on Alexander's wholeness, *Physica A*, 463, 475-484, and I may add something new into the presentation from this more recent pre-print: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1607.07169>

Leveraging Coupled Agent-Based Models to Explore the Resilience of Tightly-Coupled Land Use Systems

Patrick Bitterman¹, David A. Bennett¹

¹ University of Iowa, Iowa City, IA 52242, USA

patrick-bitterman@uiowa.edu

Abstract. This paper argues that agent-based models (ABMs) possess an inherent advantage for modeling and exploring the specified resilience of social-ecological systems. Coupled systems are often complex adaptive systems, and the ability of ABMs to integrate heterogeneous actors, dynamic couplings, and processes across spatiotemporal scales is vital to understanding resilience in the context of complexity theory. To that end, we present the results of a preliminary stylized model designed to explore resilience concepts in an agricultural land use system. We then identify strengths and opportunities for further ABM development, and outline future work to integrate empirically-parameterized agent behavioral rules with robust biophysical models to explore resilience and complexity.

Keywords: resilience, agent-based modeling, complexity, adaptive capacity

Migrant Routing in the U.S. Urban System

Xi Liu¹ and Clio Andris¹

¹ Department of Geography, The Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA, USA

{clio, xiliu}@psu.edu

Abstract. In this article, we create directional networks of U.S. core-based statistical areas where the number of nodes is equal to the number of links (edges = nodes = n) in each network. Cities link to the most popular destination city of its out-migrants for a given year. This destination city is called its cityfriend or best friend, and does not depend on migrant volume. Data is sourced from the U.S. Internal Revenue Service. The resultant networks are not fully connected but instead join cities into graph motifs or “constellations” within the galaxy of cities. We visualize these networks and create subnetworks based on wealth discrepancies. We find that the network of poorer migrants reveals a chain of local movements, which is substantially different than that of wealthy migrants, who flock to hub cities.

Keywords: migration, networks, complexity, cities, mobility

MIRACLE: A Prototype Cloud-Based Reproducible Data Analysis and Visualization Platform for Outputs of Agent-Based Models

Xiongbing Jin¹, Kirsten Robinson¹, Allen Lee², Gary Polhill³, Calvin Pritchard², and Dawn Parker¹

¹ University of Waterloo {x37jin, k4robins, dcparker}@uwaterloo.ca

² Arizona State University allen.lee@asu.edu, pritchard.calvin@gmail.com

³ The James Hutton Institute gary.polhill@hutton.ac.uk

Abstract. Since the agent-based models we design have stochastic elements and many potential parameter combinations, multiple model runs that sweep parameters are conducted, creating large quantities of computationally generated, hyper-dimensional, “big data”. Understanding the models’ implications requires structured exploration of these complex output data. In response to this need, the MIRACLE team has developed a cloud-based community platform for the management, analysis and visualization of such data, as well as the sharing of associated analysis/visualization methods and results. We anticipate that the platform will facilitate improved communication within research groups, as well as increasing access and transparency for external communities. This paper provides contextual background and a case study to the MIRACLE data storage and analysis web tool.

Keywords: reproducibility, agent-based models, big data

Spatial Informants of Modeled Phenomena: A Geospatial Analysis of Civil Violence during the Egyptian Revolution of 2011

T. Martin Smyth¹

¹ Stony Brook University, Stony Brook, New York, USA

`martin.smyth@stonybrook.edu`

Abstract. This paper seeks to model the spatial distribution of civil violence associated with political protest demonstrations during the initial period of the Egyptian revolution of 2011. A spatially constructed index of protest event visibility is introduced and a simple logistic regression analysis applied to assess its efficacy as a predictor of civil violence incidence. Agent-based models of political phenomena have been largely agnostic as to the spatial informants of modeled phenomena. The method developed in this paper is intended as an important first step toward modeling the influence of an urbanized topography as a spatial informant of political outcomes.

Keywords: protest, violence, location analytics, Egypt, Arab spring